

Malicious URL Detection Using Machine Learning

M.Venkata Krishna ^{#1}, Dr. K. V.Sambasiva Rao ^{*2}

[#] Department of CSE, NRIIT

Abstract— An address (URL) is the lifeblood of a browser; in its absence, the browser serves no use. Unfortunately, dishonest practices like phishing, hacking, and other similar activities can sometimes make use of URLs. These days, one of the simplest ways to steal personal information from consumers is to employ a malicious URL to trick them. In order to prevent users from being exposed online, it is crucial to combat such acts. When it comes to short and embedded URLs, established approaches to URL classification like black listing and heuristic classification fall short. Since our Machine Learning approach to malicious URL detection relies on feature extraction from URLs rather than on direct website access or clicks, it is significantly safer and more effective. In this study, we offer a strategy that we hope will help identify malicious URLs.

Keywords: URL, Blacklisting, Heuristic classification, Malicious URL detection, Feature extraction, Machine learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Misuse of the URL, which is fundamental to every browser, has recently grown epidemic. Obviously, no one can use a browser if they do not have a URL. However, some individuals have begun to use URL for immoral purposes. These days, it's common for malicious URLs to be hidden behind seemingly legitimate ones or to redirect users to malicious websites when they click on dangerous links. Even if the user clicks on one of these links, the hacker can still gain access to the system and cause chaos. Combating such harmful acts and protecting user information from exposure is, thus, an urgent necessity. Web, email, and networks are the most prevalent vectors by which attackers target regular people. The intended victims of phishing attacks on the web often do not realise they are being tricked into visiting malicious websites because they do not check the URL before clicking on a link. Both individuals and businesses can be reached through the mail. In order to fool company executives, phishers use false yet seemingly trustworthy information. Emails requesting personal information updates or confirmations are sent to victims with the request that they click on links within the emails. When a router is taken over and the addresses of DNS servers are modified, it results in a network medium phishing assault. Everyone using a web browser should always be on the lookout for malicious or phishing content by checking each and every URL on every page. Users should be prompted before clicking the link if it is present. Like a browser's background process, this should be checking the entire page all the time.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The detection system suggested in [1] makes use of big data technology, URL features, and a machine learning algorithm. Specifically, it employs the Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Random Forest (RF) algorithms. Using 100 trees yields better predictive results than using 10 trees. SVM takes into account all of the URL features, which impacts overall performance. Lastly, using RF with a small number of samples yields good results. The methods of Neural Networks and Machine Learning are covered in the survey [2]. While Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), and Neural Network Architecture are studied in Neural Networks, Naive Bayes, Decision Trees, Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, XGBoost, AdaBoost, and Logistic Regression are studied in Machine Learning - Naive Bayes. The survey found that neural network approaches are

more commonly employed since they expose malicious URLs upfront, while machine learning algorithms primarily aim at detection. Extracting features from URLs, such as host based features, lexical features, and site popularity features, is done in [3]. After dividing the dataset into three main types with ratios of 80:20, 70:30, and 60:40, we measured the accuracy of Support Vector Machines and Random Forest for each ratio and found that, on average, Support Vector Machines had lower accuracy than Random Forest. Regular value decomposition, distance metric learning, Nystrom techniques, DML-NYS, and NYS-DML are the five space transformation models used in the research [4]. To create new features, these five models are utilised. The article [5] explains how to identify malicious URLs by using a feature extraction method. Given that both current and previously discovered malicious URLs share a same structure, this research demonstrates how feature extraction is crucial for improving upon more conventional approaches to URL classification. Additionally, contemporary URL formats like embedded, short, and dark web URLs are undetectable by these conventional methods. The data-sets that make up the model suggested in [6] are enough to train and test it for classification purposes, and the model already contains enough data for both benign and phishing URLs. We employ three ML algorithms: Random Forest, Naive Bayes, and Logistic Regression. In this case, we train the model with three different split ratios: 1:1, 4:1, and 10:1. When comparing Logistic Regression to Naive Bayes and Random Forest, the former achieved the highest learning accuracy. A survey of the approaches used to detect rogue URLs can be found in [7]. Machine learning outperforms all other strategies when it comes to identifying dangerous URLs. In [8], we see the application of ANN, Naive Bayes (NB), and Support Vector Machine (SVM) classification algorithms. A total of 30 URL features were extracted, including 12 features based on the address bar, 6 features based on abnormalities, 5 features based on HTML, 7 features based on JavaScript, and domain-based features. When contrasted with alternative approaches, ELM (Extreme Machine Learning Algorithms) performed better. When comparing speed and performance, Support Vector Machine (SVM) wins out over Naive Bayes.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Conventional filtering methods, such as blacklisting and heuristic classification, were employed to identify malicious URLs. These antiquated methods rely on matching URL syntax and URL keywords. So, these antiquated systems aren't up to the task of handling the ever-changing URL landscape, and they also miss contemporary URLs like Embedded Links, Short URLs, and Dark Web URLs. To identify harmful URLs, the suggested categorization method employs a machine learning system. There are two parts to the model, as shown in Figure 1: the training phase and the detection phase. In the training phase, features are retrieved from the collection of URLs (both good and bad) and assigned a value of '0' for non-malicious URLs and a value of '1' for malicious URLs. Extractions include features based on the Address Bar, features based on the Domain, and features based on HTML and JavaScript. A machine learning method is used to train these URLs. Stage of Detection: A user-entered URL is first parsed for its properties, which are then used

to determine if the URL is "Good" (a safe URL) or "Bad" (a malicious URL). Here, the model's accuracy will be tested based on its predictions Shown in **FIGURE 1**.

Fig1:Malicious URL Detection Model using Machine Learning

IV.METHODOLOGY

There are two steps of machine learning technique .The first step is to assign correct feature through feature extraction so that it could give the deciding bits of knowledge (Legitimate-0, Phishing-1) in finding Malicious URLs and the next step is to use the above features to train a Machine Learning Algorithm. Here we will be classifying the URLs based on the features extracted from them. In this paper we have used Address Bar based features, Domain based features and HTML and JavaScript based features. The reason of using Address Bar based features, Domain based features and HTML and JavaScript based features is that even most of the new evolving URLs generated today should follow the same structure like the existing system. **In Figure 2.**, we have discussed the flow and working of our model. The first phase of our model is collection of Benign (Open-SourceDataset) and Malicious URLs(PhistankDataset) to form dataset. Total 10,000 URLs are used to form dataset. The complete dataset is stored using CSV format.

Malicious URLs: - Randomly 5,000 Malicious URLs are collected from open source service called phish tank to train ML models.

Legitimate URLs: -Randomly 5,000 Legitimate URLs are collected from open datasets of University of New Brunswick.

The second phase of the workflow is extraction of features. Total 15 features of URLs are extracted.

Table 1. shows 15 features along with feature group and data type. Eight Address Bar based, four Domain based and three HTML and JavaScript based features are extracted. All features except depth of URL is of Boolean data type where as depth of URL is of numeric data type. Malicious URLs are labelled as '1' and

Legitimate URLs are labelled as ‘0’. In the third phase of the workflow the labelled data collected which consists of Benign and Phishing URLs undergoes the process of feature extraction where the various features are extracted, and then, the data are divided into Training dataset and the Testing dataset. We have divided training and testing data in two ratios 80:20 and 70:30. In the next phase, the model is trained by passing the training data through various models such as XGBoost and RandomForest Algorithms. In this paper we have used two Supervised Machine Learning Algorithm XGBoost and Random Forest which is discussed in literature. Then, the Trained model is tested using the Testing dataset. In the query phase user inputs, the URL that has to be classified. Input URL’s feature is extracted and the output is ‘1’ if the URL is Malicious and ‘0’ if the URL is Legitimate.

Figure 2: Workflow & Working Model

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 3. and **Figure 4.** shows the feature importance graph of RF which tells that RF considers “https://:” in URL part feature as an important. IT displays the dataset's split ratios, training data accuracy, testing data accuracy, and combined testing duration. The Random Forest and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) algorithms were utilised. According to the results, XGBoost outperforms Random Forest, particularly when the split ratio is 80:20. Among the attributes used to categorise URLs, the feature importance graph of Random Forest reveals that HTTPs token is a crucial component, as shown in Figures 3 and 4. Figures 5 and 6 display the Extreme Gradient Boost Algorithm's feature importance graph. In this case, prefix/suffix is considered the most important information for categorization, however have IP and HTTPs token are also significant. Much better and more accurate results for URL classification are generated by these three crucial qualities

Figure 3:RF(70:30)

Figure 4:RF(80:20)

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we demonstrated how to train an ML model to detect malicious and legitimate URLs using the URL's properties. Our categorization algorithm will definitely provide better results when conventional methods miss the mark when it comes to detecting freshly emerging URLs. We also looked at how well various Machine Learning Algorithms classified the URL and discovered that XGBoost performed the best. In order to train the Machine Learning model with more data and additional URL attributes for better and more accurate outcomes, this effort will expand in the future. Additional training of the model can enable it to identify Dark Web pages. Additionally, it is possible to create a browser extension for this purpose, allowing the process to dynamically filter malicious websites while running continually in the background.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would like to express our gratitude to NRI Institute of Technology for providing the necessary resources and support for conducting this research. Special thanks to our colleagues and research team members for their valuable insights and contributions throughout the project.

REFERENCES

- [1] Cho Do Xuan, Hoa Dinh Nguyen, Tisenko Victor Nikolaevich, (2020) "Malicious URL Detection based on Machine Learning", *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*.
- [2] Eint Sandi Aung, Hayato Yamana, (2020) "Malicious URL Detection: A Survey", *Department of Computer Science and Communication Engineering, Graduate School of Fundamental Science and Engineering*.
- [3] Ripon Patgiri, Hemanth Katari, Ronit Kumar and Dheeraj Sharma, (2020) "Empirical Study on Malicious URL Detection Using Machine Learning", *International Conference, ICDICT*.
- [4] Tie Li, Gang Kou, Yi Peng (2020) "Improving Malicious URLs Detection via Feature Engineering: Linear and nonlinear Space Transformation Methods", *Information Systems (Elsevier)*.
- [5] Immadisetti Naga Venkata Durga Naveen, Manamohana K, Rohit Verma, (2019) "Detection of Malicious URLs using Machine Learning Techniques", *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE)*.
- [6] Vanitha N and Vinodhini V, (2019) "Malicious URL Detection using Logistic Regression Technique", *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research*.
- [7] Lekshmi A R, Seena Thomas (2019) "Detecting Malicious URLs Using Machine Learning Techniques: A Comparative Literature Review", *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*.
- [8] Yasin Sonmez, Turker Tuncer, Huseyin Gokal, Engin Avci (2018) "Phishing Web Sites Features Classification Based on Extreme Learning Machine", *6th International Symposium on Digital Forensic and Security (ISDFS)*.